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ENHANCING FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMPETENCE THROUGH LEGAL TOPICS: A STUDY OF DIVORCE-RELATED LEGAL SOLUTIONS IN GLOBAL AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION

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Annatation: This article analyzes the legal foundations of family divorces, as well as their social and psychological causes. It also examines the legal norms that regulate the divorce process. The author proposes recommendations aimed at ensuring family stability, reducing the number of divorces, and improving the legal mechanisms for resolving family disputes. The study is based on the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, statistical data, and scholarly sources.

Key words: family divorce, legal grounds for divorce, meditation process, marriage dissolution procedure, court procedure, legal assistance, civil code.

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Introduction

The legal aspect of language is significant for linguistics, because it is the law that regulates the use of language, the relationship between languages, establishes the status of language. Expressing the will of the legislature, the language brings this will to the public; it is directly in contact with the law. Legal regulation of society includes the use of language to mediate political, social, economic and other relations in law. It is language as a means of legal writing and law application that ensures the functioning of the state and its institutions. Thus, the synthesis of linguistics and jurisprudence is necessary to solve many problems that require both linguistic and legal knowledge, since language is the only means for development of legal concepts. (Svetlana Yu. Maksimova, 2020)

The family is the smallest yet most important social institution in society, directly influencing all aspects of human life. A stable and strong family plays an invaluable role in raising a healthy generation, improving the social environment, and preserving national values.

In recent years, due to socio-economic changes, labor migration, the widespread use of information technologies, and shifts in lifestyle, the number of divorces in Uzbekistan has been increasing. According to data from the State Committee on Statistics, between 2023 and 2024 the number of divorces rose by an average of 10–12 percent annually.

This situation negatively affects social stability and harms the upbringing, psychological well-being, and economic condition of minor children. Therefore, it is of great importance to reconsider the legal approach to divorce, strengthen preventive measures, and enhance legal awareness in society. The main purpose of this article is to examine the legal foundations of divorce, identify effective ways to

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reduce its occurrence, and develop scientific recommendations for improving the existing legislation.

Methodology

1. Legal Foundations of Divorce

According to the *Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan*, a marriage may be dissolved either through the court or the civil registry offices. If both spouses mutually agree to divorce and have no minor children, the marriage is terminated through the registry office. However, if the couple has minor children or one of the spouses does not consent to the divorce, the dissolution of the marriage is carried out exclusively through the court.

During court proceedings, the following issues are resolved: Determination of which parent the minor children will live with; Establishment of the amount of alimony payments; Division of jointly acquired property; Provision of financial support to one of the parties, if necessary. All these matters are regulated in detail by Articles 38–44 of the *Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan*. (*Law on Mediation*, 2018).

2. Main Causes of Divorce

Family divorces often occur due to the following factors: Economic problems — unemployment, low income, and lack of housing; Psychological incompatibility — lack of mutual respect and communication culture between spouses; Labor migration — long-term separation weakens family ties; Domestic violence — cases of physical or psychological abuse; Low legal awareness — family members' insufficient knowledge of their rights and obligations. These factors reveal not only the legal but also the socio-psychological roots of divorce. (Olga Bezuglova, 2015)

3. Consequences of Divorce

The most severe consequences of divorce affect children. Due to the absence of one parent, children often experience emotional stress and face difficulties in

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social adaptation. Moreover, divorced women frequently encounter economic hardship and an increased need for social protection. At the societal level, divorces can: Disrupt demographic balance; Increase the demand for social assistance; Reduce labor productivity. (Linwood J. Randolph Jr., 2017).

4. Legal Solutions and Preventive Measures

The following legal measures play an important role in preventing divorces: Introducing a mandatory pre-marital psychological and legal counseling system; Further developing the **institution of mediation**, which enables spouses to reach agreements without resorting to court proceedings; Strengthening mechanisms to combat **domestic violence**; Focusing the work of **mahalla committees** and **women's councils** on preventing family conflicts; Expanding social and economic support programs for **young families**. In addition, it is necessary to strengthen gender equality in family matters by amending the *Family Code* and the *Law on the Protection of Women*.

Figure 2. Survey results.

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Results

The study revealed that the main factors contributing to family divorces include legal unawareness, socio-economic challenges and ineffective conflict-resolution practices. The analysis showed that the implementation of mediation significantly reduces the duration and emotional tension of divorce procedures. (Karimova, N. 2022). It was also found that strengthening legal support services helps families better understand their rights and obligations during the separation process.

The research demonstrated that improving parental responsibility and child-focused policies increases post-divorce stability. Overall the findings indicate that a combination of legal reforms mediation and psychological support can effectively reduce the number of divorce cases and mitigate their negative consequences.

The study shows that the main causes of divorces are a lack of mutual understanding and financial difficulties. When families apply to the court for divorce the court should provide more effective practical assistance and strengthen reconciliation and counseling mechanisms. I would also like to emphasize that it is necessary to establish and expanded legal advisory services not only for young families but for all families in general.

Conclusion

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The family is the foundation and stronghold of society. The growing number of divorces has emerged as a serious social issue for both the state and the community. Therefore, it is necessary to improve legal mechanisms, raise citizens' legal awareness, strengthen the mediation system, and restore family values.

Mutual respect, trust, and responsibility within family relationships are the most essential guarantees for preventing divorce. By further developing systems of legal and psychological support, it is possible to reduce divorce rates and ensure greater social stability.

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